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STRATEGIC ANALYSIS AND STRATEGIC FORMULATION: IMPLICATIONS IN THE NIGERIAN PORTS AUTHORITYI

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Abstract

This study was carried out to forestall operational inefficiency, laxity, and ineffectiveness in the Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA). The resource-based stream of the Business Development Theory was adopted as the theoretical framework for the study. The methodology used in this research was the historical/descriptive survey design. The methods of enquiry included the primary and secondary methods of data collection. Two subsidiary objectives were set, such as: to broaden the minds of the participants, particularly some of the newly promoted ones who may not have been very conversant with the core mandates of the organisation from the time of their employment with the need for efficiency and effectiveness in the agency; and, to refresh the memories of those other participants that may have been very versatile with the workings of the NPA from the time of their employment with the core mandates of the organisation. In order to elicit answers from respondents, two research questions were asked based on the subsidiary objectives above. The research hypotheses were also postulated based on the two research questions to enable empirical verifications in the study. The collected data were analysed using the class participation approach, involving a total of 60 participants: 40 managers and 20 general managers of the NPA. The findings of the study were also in two folds, upon which the two recommendations were based. The recommendations were that the Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA) should continue to conduct similar trainings for all its staff. This was because, from the above finding, it was pertinent for NPC to know that the reason for the lapses such as inefficiency, laxity, and ineffectiveness in the agency was because some of the newly promoted participants had not been very conversant with the core mandates of the organisation from the time of their employment. It was recommended that the Federal Government should, as a matter of urgency, embark on a periodic re-orientation of the entire workforce of the NPA (from the lowest to the highest cadre of the agency), especially now that the mother ministry in which the NPA was domiciled has metamorphosed from the Federal Ministry of Transport to the Federal Ministry of Marine and Blue Economy.

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Introduction

The theme, "Strategy Excellence: From Strategic Vision to Tactical Execution" was broken into sub-topics and treated by different lecturers during a 5-day training programme organised by Top-Idea Global Resources for Managers and General Managers of the Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA) in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, from January 8th to 12, 2024. One set of the sub-topics "Strategic Analysis and Strategic Formulation: Implications in the Nigerian Ports Authority I and II" (as modified) was discussed one after the other on the second day of the training, precisely on the 9th day of January 2024, by Dr. Unwana-Abasi Udoh of the Department of Public Administration in the Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus, Nigeria. It would be noted that the sub-topics: Strategic Analysis and Strategic Formulation (I) and Strategic Analysis and Strategic Formulation (II), as earlier mentioned, were divided into two parts. Both parts were treated on the same day, as Part I and Part II. In other words, in Part I, emphasis was on "Strategic Analysis", while in Part II, "Strategic Formulation was emphasised".

However, in a nutshell, while strategic analysis refers to an evaluation of an organisation's work environment, strategic formulation is the process of establishing goals and determining the proper plan of action to achieve those goals. The Mafia Manager: A Guide to the Corporate Machiavelli by "V" provides thought-provoking counsel below, which will serve as a great guide to us in our discussion today. The author posits further that, "In business, the golden rule is that whoever has the most power makes the rules and takes the gold. According to the Corporate Machiavelli:

The bedrock secret of success can be summarised as this: Find a place in the system where you manage others. To find such a place, if you start with no inherited wealth, you must be more intelligent, ambitious and vigorous than your competition. And if you are to succeed greatly in the world, you must also be lucky and ruthless. Live with wolves, and you will learn to howl.

But, in the "Prince," a Penguin Classics, Niccolo Machiavelli deduces "a general rule that never or rarely fails to apply: that whoever is responsible for another's

becoming powerful ruins himself, because this power is brought into being either by ingenuity or by force, and both of these sumits to the one who has become powerful".

And whereas Machiavelli further pontificates on the wisdom behind succeeding in business, thus:

- i. If the pot is boiling over, use a long spoon;
- ii. If the house is on fire, warm yourself;
- iii. Mind your own business, but keep your eyes on other businesses;
- iv. If your neighbour gets up early, you get up earlier;
- v. Never give business advice to another that doesn't profit you and your interests;
- vi. And never act on business advice given- you without second and third opinions.

Statement of the Problem

It is on record that the Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA) was vested with the responsibility to carry out the following statutory duties and functions: develop, own, and operate ports and harbours; provide a safe and navigable channel; offer cargo handling and storage services; maintain port facilities and equipment; ensure safety and security; and develop and own property. But it has been observed that this system has greatly hindered port development and curtailed operational efficiency. The ports became less competitive and a conduit to drain the meagre national resources. In an attempt to change this trend, the activities of the Authority (NPA) were commercialised and offered greater autonomy in accordance with the recommendation of the Technical Committee on Privatisation and Commercialization. However, this could not bring the expected improvement because of the public service bureaucracy and interference. It was later revised to its initial status.

But, in an effort to reposition and enhance the national economy, the Federal Government embarked on various reform initiatives in the public sector, which includes the maritime sub-sector. This initiative was to foster an economy that is responsive, robust, private sector-oriented, and in line with international best practices. In line with the reform programme, the transactions commenced with the advertisement for Expression of Interest EOIs on the 3rd of December 2003, by the National Council on Privatisation, with the Bureau of Public Enterprises acting as the transaction agent. A total of 110 EOIs were harvested, out of which 94 were pre-qualified.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to diagnose the implications of strategic analysis and strategic formulation for the Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA). The subsidiary objectives included:

- i. To broaden the knowledge of the participants, particularly some of the newly

- promoted ones who may not have been very conversant with the core mandates of the organisation from the time of their employment with the need for efficiency and effectiveness in the agency; and,
- ii. To refresh the memories of other participants that may have been very versatile with the workings of the NPA from the time of their employment with the core mandates of the organisation and with the current economic realities in the country.

Research Questions

The following will serve as research questions put forward to elicit answers from respondents:

- i. Why are some of the newly promoted participants not have been very conversant with the core mandates of the organisation from the time of their employment about the need for efficiency and effectiveness in the agency?
- ii. Is there any need to refresh the memories of those other participants that may have been very versatile with the workings of the NPA from the time of their employment, with the core mandates of the organisation and with the current economic realities in the country?

Research Hypotheses

The research hypotheses were postulated based on the two research questions above:

- i. Some of the newly promoted participants may likely not have been very conversant with the core mandates of the organisation from the time of their employment about the need for efficiency and effectiveness in the agency.
- ii. There may be no need to refresh the memories of other participants that may have been very versatile with the workings of the NPA from the time of their employment with the core mandates of the organisation and with the current economic realities in the country.

Methodology

The methodology used in this research was the historical/descriptive survey design. The methods of enquiry included the primary and secondary methods of data collection. The data collected were primarily analysed using the class participation approach, involving a total of 60 participants: 40 managers and 20 general managers of the NPA. Whereas, the secondary sources of data included text books, publications, journals, and the internet.

Theoretical Explications

The theory of business development was adopted in the study. Although this theory has five (5) variances, namely: resource-based theory, complexity theory, complex network theory, statistical learning theory, and games theory, the resource-based theory was found to be the most appropriate and was adopted in this study.

Resource-based Theory

Resource-based theory evolved as a way to help understand how strategic resources and capabilities usually allow organisations to enjoy excellent performance. Since its emergence in the 1990's, the resource-based theory does gain--typically in action and with contention that the possession of strategic resources provides an organisation with a golden opportunity to develop competitive advantages over its rivals. Though remarkably, resource-based theory never became relevant in firms' strategic measures until 1980's; this was simply because of its framework concepts that have focused directly on external issues. At present, with strong indications recently, it is observed that resource-based theory has gained maturity of some worth that's to be adopted by scholars instead of resource-based view approach (Barney, 2001). Subsequently many scholars have themed out that somehow, that resource-based theory perspective was evident from the 1930's, involving the works of Barney which was comprehensively inclined by Wernerfelt's work, which thereafter presented the indication of resource position hurdles that are related to entry barriers in the positioning school. But according to several scholars, more work did suggest that the resource-based theory denotes innovative paradigm to businesses with backgrounds in 'Ricardian and Penrosian' economic theories that were agreeing to what businesses can make has sustainable returns on investment (ROI) and comparable, indicates that competitive advantages in turn can help the organisation to enjoy strong profits/revenue for reason that a strategic resource is classified to be an asset that is valuable, rare, difficult to imitate and quite non-substitutable and makeup to an extent whereby it will help organisation to develop distinct strategies that make the most of target opportunities and ward off threats to make profits (Barney, Wright, & Ketchen, 2001; Hunt, 2013).

Application of the Business Development Theories to the NPA Business Environment

The applicability of the business theories to the NPA business environment has made it possible to discuss and as well as task several changes with strategic management techniques that occur in business performance processes from the early 1940s' engaging in various improving activities and functioning to boost organisations' revenue and key

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performing methods through strategic decision techniques such as downsizing, outsourcing, benchmarking, economic value analysis, total quantity management, re-engineering, and others in order to enable the business world to primarily do something differently with several business theories to develop business tools and techniques. Developing business tools and techniques is simply considered a centre of challenges that determine or makeup the applicability of business theories for organisations' management and executives, and especially for those operations of large organisations compared to small organisations in terms of the practicality of techniques and theories relevancies that would envisage long-term success for business operations (Drucker, 1994). In conclusion, Spulber (2009) argues that business theories as concepts have been an appropriate platform for observing everyday business operations, including large and small organisations, in relation to the theory of business as it connects with economics, technology, philosophy, and other subjects or fields to explaining and predicting the nature of operational businesses' efficiency and likewise focus on its applicability to the business environment that considers aspects such as;

- Business action plan
- Business-behavioural strategy
- Business structure method
- Market environment system
- Economics of scale
- Global business fiction
- Strategic dominance and competitive advantage
- Collective business system
- Balancing short-term and long-term pay-outs
- Defining good and bad capital
- Knowing what customers want to buy

Significance of the Study

The significance of the study is categorised into two perspectives, namely theoretical and empirical significance.

I. Theoretical significance:

The research will contribute immensely to the existing body of knowledge, and as such, it will serve as reference materials for future researchers both in NPA and in the entire public corporation.

ii. Empirical significance:

The knowledge acquired from the study on the implications of strategic analysis and strategic formulation in the Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA) will help to proffer a lasting solution to the recurrent problem of inefficiency and ineffectiveness in the NPA. It is hoped that the actual cause of inefficiency and ineffectiveness in the organisation will be identified in the course of this research. Therefore, the study will offer experts solution to nip the problem on the board. The Legislature will find this material useful in making relevant legislations that will preserve NPA infrastructure and promote and revitalise the entire corporation as well as other government agencies. The executive will realise the importance of preserving government equity share in the organisation and, as such, will beef up strict supervision and security on the agency.

Definition of Concepts

- i. Strategic Analysis:** Strategic analysis refers to an evaluation of an organisation's work environment.
- ii. Strategic Formulation:** Strategic formulation is the process of establishing goals and determining the proper plan of action to achieve those goals.
- iii. Implications:** The term "implications" refers to impact or effects (positive or negative) on a phenomenon. Implications may also refer to what something implies, means or stand for (Udoh, *et al.*, 2023).
- iv. Nigerian Ports Authority:** Nigerian Ports Authority is an agency or a corporation of the Federal Government of Nigeria vested with the responsibility to develop, own, and operate ports and harbours; provide safe and navigable channels; offer cargo handling and storage services; maintain port facilities and equipment; ensure safety and security; and develop and own property.

The Core Mandates of the Nigerian Ports Authority

The Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA) has the following as its core mandates:

- Ownership and administration of land and water within port limits.
- Planning and development of port operational infrastructure.
- Leasing and concession of port infrastructure and setting a benchmark for tariff structure.
- Responsible for nautical and harbour operations and hydrographic surveys.
- Marine incidents and pollution.
- Maintenance of safety and security in the common user areas.
- Enacting port regulations and bye-laws as well as monitoring and enforcing them.
- Day-to-day monitoring of operations and enforcement of relevant sections of

respective agreements.

- Towage, mooring, bunkering, ship chandelling, and ship repairs.

Others are:

- Cargo handling, stevedoring, warehousing, and delivery.
- Acquisition of cargo handling and operations-related equipment.
- Development and maintenance of ports' superstructure.
- Maintenance of safety and security within the terminal.

Why is strategic analysis important?

Most of the ever-growing organisations implemented strategic planning through various phases of their business. The analysis is a part of business planning that has a systematic strategy and appropriate resource investment and can help you reach your goal as an organisation.

One of the main characteristics is that it makes you consider your competitors and helps you evaluate your business strategies to keep you on top of the race. It is important because it highlights the internal and external factors that influence the organization. By evaluating the organisation, you can formulate and implement strategies. The analysis is part of strategic planning along with strategy formulation. The analysis sets the stage for you to formulate strategies and make decisions.

Merits of Strategic Analysis

- i. Strategic analysis allows you to have clarity about the internal positive attributes of the organisation that are under control. By knowing these positive attributes, an organisation can focus on the factors that lead to positive performance and replicate the strategy wherever applicable.
- ii. It helps identify the strengths of both internal and external resources, which leads to an increasing competitive advantage.
- iii. It offers you the internal components that add value or offer a competitive advantage to your business. When you have a reasonable competitive advantage over your competitors, half the game plan is clear. The only aspect that would need clarity is what is not going the company's way.

Demerits of Strategic Analysis

- i. Strategic analysis can generate too many ideas, but it does not help to choose which one is the best.
- ii. Sometimes too much time is spent on existential problem solving, such that there is little or no time left for innovating new products or making service

level changes at the organisational level.

Having laid the above background on the subject, we can now take the concepts one by one using the following sub-topics: analysing internal organisational capabilities and resources; evaluating core competencies and competitive advantage; considering value chain analysis and identifying strengths and weaknesses of the organisation; and particularly, embarking on SWOT Analysis – i.e., internal strategic analysis.

1. Analysing Internal Organisational Capabilities and Resources: To analyse internal organisational capabilities and resources is to ask the fundamental question: What is strategic analysis? Strategic analysis refers to an evaluation of an organisation's work environment. This work environment generally defines how the organisation operates its business. It helps to determine the mood and functioning of the organisation and whether the goals and objectives set by the organisation can be met. Many experts advise conducting it in an organisation from time to time. It can help uncover the areas that need changes and enhancements.

Furthermore, strategic analysis is a process that involves researching an organisation's business environment, within which it operates. Strategic analysis is essential to formulating strategic planning for decision-making and smooth working of that organization. With the help of strategic planning, the objectives or goals that are set by the organisation can be fulfilled. In a constant strive to improve, organisations must periodically conduct a strategic analysis, which will, in turn, help them determine what areas need improvement and those that are already doing well. For an organisation to function efficiently, it is important to think about how positive changes need to be implemented.

Strategic analysis is essential if a company has a goal and a mission for itself. All leading organisations that are well known for their achievements have years of strategic planning being implemented at various stages. Strategic planning is a long-term task involving continuous and systematic planning and resource investment. The main question that a company should consider when performing a strategic analysis is: How is the market constituted? How are the active clients in this sector? While conducting strategic analysis, organisations must know their competitors and thus be able to define a strategy that will make them an unbeatable player in that market. One of the most important functions of strategic planning is to predict future events and deduce alternative strategies if a certain plan doesn't work out as expected.

2. Evaluating core competencies and competitive advantage

This will lead us to the types of strategic analysis, which are basically two types, namely:

internal and external strategic analysis.

Internal Strategic Analysis: As the name suggests, through this analysis, organisations look inwards or within the organisation, identify the positive and negative points, and establish the set of resources that can be used to improve the company's image within the market. Internal analysis starts with evaluating the core competencies and competitive advantages. It deals with evaluating the performance of the organisation. This includes evaluating the potential of an organisation and its capacity to grow.

The analysis of the strengths of the company should be oriented towards the market, focusing on the client. The strengths only make sense when they help the company fulfil its clients' needs. When doing an internal strategic analysis, one should also know the weaknesses and limitations that a company faces, either currently or in the future.

3. Value Chain Analysis and Identifying Strengths and Weaknesses

A value chain is a progression of activities that a firm operating in a specific industry performs in order to deliver a valuable product (i.e., good and/or service) to the end customer. In a study conducted by yours truly with a co-researcher to tackle and proffer solutions to recurrent power outages usually witnessed along Aba and Itu National Grid that threw the entire Uyo and Eket metropolitan cities and their environs into total blackout, thereby impacting gross negative implications on the socio-economic development of the entire area, about four (4) dimensions of practical effects of power outage were studied. The findings were a great indictment on the Port Harcourt Electricity Distribution Company (PHED), as its value chain was grossly impeded by the incessant power outages.

For the sake of further clarifications, it could be useful if those dimensions of value chain analyses in the Port Harcourt Electricity Distribution Company (PHED) are brought up in this study.

The first dimension was **the implications of value chain on small and medium-scale businesses**. A problem on the national grid is a problem on the entire sphere of operation of such a grid. A problem on the national grid is a total blackout on a large spectrum of area, in and around the location of the problem to as far as the extent of its coverage. Lately, it has been observed that the Aba and Itu national grids have been faced with incessant power outages to the extent that the entire Uyo metropolis, as well as Eket and their environs, were thrown into total blackout during these periods for a number of days before the problem was rectified.

First, it happened in the middle of May 2023, and second, it occurred between Tuesday, June 27th, and ended in the evening of Friday, June 30th, 2023. Chances are

that the incident may occur again and again, unless a permanent solution is found. This incident might have occurred as a result of the heavy rain that fell almost uninterruptedly in parts of the state from Tuesday, June 27th, up to Thursday, June 29th, 2023. This incident has caused the state a serious setback in terms of its socio-economic development.

For example, the situation has brought untold hardship on the citizenry and on the masses, particularly the electricity users; small and medium-scale businesses (SMEs), which drive the bulk of the societal economy, were seriously slowed down or temporarily folded up. Before now, almost every business was able to switch on its private generating set to power its business premises in the event of a power failure. But, in recent times, due to the high cost of premium motor spirit, also known as petrol, which is caused by the recent subsidy removal by the Tinubu-led federal government on May 31, most businesses have suffered serious losses in buying fuel to run their generators and provide the same services hitherto provided for their customers. At the end of the scenario, it is the customers who bear the final burden of paying more for the services they received. Furthermore, other small and medium-scale businesses like commodity shops, barber/hairdressing saloons, laundry/dry cleaning shops, phones/laptops charging stations, other business centres for internet operations, typing, photocopying, scanning, and lamination; printing press; private schools; and hotels, etc. that should move the economy of the state forward on a day-to-day basis were stalled, slowed down, or temporarily closed down because of a lack of electricity.

The implications of value chain on private/family lives were the second dimension.

A particular focus is on the private and family lives of the citizens of the state in the two cosmopolitan towns, Uyo and Eket, as mentioned earlier, which were observed during the period under study to have been seriously jeopardized. It was observed that many private homes were no longer able to afford petrol to power their generators due to the high cost of the commodity. The few that still maintain their status quo only manage to do so. Some families commit almost their entire monthly earnings or family business finances to providing electricity in their homes. Others who cannot afford to purchase the highly expensive petrol to run their generators no longer enjoy fans and air conditioners. Their homes are devoid of good ventilation. As such, they suffer from heat, especially during the dry season. Excessive heat, in turn, can cause some health challenges like heat rashes, dehydration, draught, soar-throat, etc.

Also, in such homes, their food and cooked foods, especially soups, could easily get soured as their refrigerators and deep freezers no longer function due to a lack of electricity. Another major challenge to the value chain in private homes is the issue of

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water. Of course, it is often said that “water is life.” As most families depend on their private water supply, most of them, during those periods of power outages, struggled to pump water from their boreholes due to the high cost of fuel or diesel. Those who insisted kept depleting their family income. But those families that cannot afford to run their private generators to power their systems are thrown into what the authors call “new dependency.”

The third dimension was the implications of value chain on independence. This factor has caused many citizens who had managed to be self-sufficient, self-reliant, and independent to be thrown back to what the authors call “**new dependency.**” By new dependency, it means that some citizens who were capable of taking care of themselves and their families were compelled by the current realities to seek out new friends in the neighbourhood who could help charge their phones, laptops, and other rechargeable instruments in the neighbours' houses for them because the friends were able to provide an alternative source of power unlike them. The implication is that dependency, being what it is (whether old or new), would not allow for rapid growth and development of individuals and society.

The implications of value chain on the safety, security, and nightlife of citizens were the final dimension. The safety of the lives and property of Nigerians at this time can no longer be guaranteed. This is because the recent pronouncement by President Asiwaju Bola Tinubu on the removal of fuel subsidy has caused a sudden and uncontrollable economic crisis in the country. Apart from the independent fuel marketers taking over the economy and selling fuel at exorbitant and uncontrollable prices, this situation has caused a sudden and unabated proliferation of black marketeering in the country. In all major roads, streets, corners, and junctions in all cities and villages today in Nigeria, these hawkers are selling fuel between N600.00 and N750.00, depending on what part of the country you are buying the product from.

On the other hand, it is common knowledge that crimes thrive more in the cover of darkness than they do in broad daylight. During those periods of power outages under study, there were cases of pickpocketing and snatching of handbags and phones from unsuspecting passers-by mostly at Uyo By-pass as well as at Itam Flyover and Akpan Andem Market. Some tricyclists were also reported to have rubbed some of their passengers as they drove them pass their bus stop to unknown destinations without their knowledge due to darkness on the road. Security lights along the Goodluck Jonathan Bullavat (the new stadium road) in particular were removed as the whole area was dark due to a lack of electricity in the town.

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The new ring road, from the newly constructed roundabout at Aka Road down to the water fountain at Oron Road in Uyo metropolis, was a safe haven for criminals to operate unchallenged from about 7 p.m. upward. Cases of car snatches were reported at the Atiku Abubarka flyover at about 7 p.m. during the period. Several incidents of criminal activities were also reported to have taken place in Eket town during that period, particularly in and around Grace Bill and the re-modelling environments. There were cases of bags and phones being snatched from the unsuspecting public.

Finally, the nightlife of the citizens was at risk as hoodlums had a fair deal in the streets under the cover of darkness. The usual business environment, like Maitama in Ewet Housing Estate and other sit-outs and eateries, were operating at a skeletal level. Most people were afraid to leave their houses at night to go out, while those who had left homes since daytime hastened back before getting late. Finally, as nightclubs, sit-outs, and eateries powered their drinks to be cold with their plants, so also were the prices of drinks raised. For instance, Champion and 33 Export Larger Beer were raised from N400.00 and N500.00, the initial prices, respectively, to N500.00 and N600.00 per bottle, respectively, in some sit-outs in Uyo and Eket. The prices might not have returned after the restoration of light in the city".

4. SWOT Analysis: Internal Strategic Analysis

SWOT analysis is one of the most reputed techniques for internal strategic analysis. There is no better way to benefit from a strategically performed analysis than to use it to detect the **strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats** that your project may suffer.

Performing SWOT analysis will help you create a strong and long-term vision through strategic planning for your organisation. The important thing is to constantly evaluate the environment in which the company operates and act accordingly. It is essential for an organisation to take into account the SWOT principle in order to be able to plan efficiently. Through a thorough SWOT analysis, companies will be able to prevent a number of problems that can arise if there is no systematic analysis.

Let us further break down these attributes and understand how an organisation can conduct a complete strategic analysis to be able to plan and perform better with each passing year.

Strengths of a company: There are several attributes within the company that are positive and that you can control in order to obtain better results; they are your strengths, which make you stand out from others. Surely there are certain resources or strategies that have led to your organisation's process year on year. Knowing these resources or strategies is also considered a strength. Knowing this type of information is very

important because these are the elements that give you an advantage over your competition.

Business weakness: It is practically impossible for an organisation or a company to have only strengths and not have weaknesses. Therefore, there are certain characteristics of an organisation that need to be improved in order to be able to perform better and compete in the market. These are called business weaknesses. Most of the factors are foreseeable, and an organisation needs to identify them well in advance and approach the problems with a corrective measure.

Threats to an organisation: There are going to be some negative factors that will affect the growth of the organisation, and these factors can be analysed too. These factors need to be detected, and a risk management strategy needs to be put in place so that threats like stronger brand value of the competitors, better relationships between competitors and retailers, etc. don't have an adverse effect on the company's growth. Also, threats like multiple players in the market with the same products, a downturn in the economy, and better advertising of the same product by competitors are some threats that have to be dealt with carefully so that competitors don't take advantage of the situation.

Opportunities for the company: Detect the opportunities you have to grow. Knowing the path organisations must follow is a great step towards success. Take advantage of all those external factors that are positive for the organisation. Identify all the opportunities and take advantage of them.

Summary of Findings

Based on the two hypotheses postulated in this study, a participant inquiry method was adopted in the class by the lecturer, thereby affording the managers and general managers of NPA that attended the training the opportunity to interact during the interactive session. During the interactive session, it was found that:

- I. Some of the newly promoted participants have not been very conversant with the core mandates of the organisation from the time of their employment about the need for efficiency and effectiveness in the agency.
- ii. There was a need to refresh the memories of other participants who may have been very versatile with the workings of the NPA from the time of their employment, with the core mandates of the organisation, and with the current economic realities in the country.

Conclusion

In conclusion, having perused the core mandates of NPA in relation to the various sub-topics treated above, which included analysing internal organisational capabilities and resources; evaluating core competencies and competitive advantage; considering value chain analysis and identifying strengths and weaknesses of the organisation; and, particularly, embarking on SWOT analysis, i.e., internal strategic analysis, it behoves on us to ask ourselves a pertinent question: what are the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats that our organisation is exposed to in the present economic reality in the country?

Indeed, there are several strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats that your organisation is exposed to, especially now that the NPA has been moved from the Federal Ministry of Transportation to the Federal Ministry of Marine and Blue Economy. That alone presents the agency with some robust strengths, untold weaknesses, great opportunities, and incessant threats. To be able to harness the strengths, overcome the weaknesses, maximize the available opportunities, and combat the threats, an organisation must be repositioned on a new pedestal to surmount the challenges and strive for a greater achievement, which is the bedrock of every business organisation. Therefore, as you consciously work both individually and corporately toward achieving these goals, the Lecturer wishes you all the best in your endeavours. See you at the next Lecture!

Recommendations:

As a result of the two (2) findings made in the study, it was recommended that;

- i. Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA) should continue to conduct similar trainings for all its staff to broaden their knowledge. This is because the research shows that it is pertinent for NPC to know that the reason for the lapses, such as inefficiency and ineffectiveness in the agency was because some of the newly promoted participants have not been very conversant with the core mandates of the organisation from the time of their employment about the need for efficiency and effectiveness in the agency.

- ii. Federal Government should, as a matter of urgency, embark on a periodic re-orientation of the entire workforce of NPA (from the lowest to the highest cadre of the agency), especially now that the mother Ministry that NPA was domiciled has metamorphosed from Federal Ministry of Transport to Federal Ministry of Marine and Blue Economy.

References

- Barney, J.B. (2001). Is the Resource Based View a Useful Perspective for Strategic Management Research? *Academy of Management Review*. 26 (1): 102. doi:10.5465/AMR.2001.4011938.
- Barney, J. B., Wright, M., & Ketchen, D. J. (2001). The Resource Based View of the Firm: Ten years after 1991. *Journal of Management*, 27: 625-43.
- Hunt, S.D. (2013). A General Theory of Business Marketing: R-A theory, Alderson, the ISBM Framework and the IMP Theoretical Structure. *Industrial Marketing Management* 41: 283-293.
- Machiavelli, N. (1999). *The Prince*. Penguin Books. London, England.
- Nigeria Ports Authority website <https://nigerianports.gov.ng/history/our-mandate/>
- Spulber, D.F (2009). *The Theory of the Firm*, Cambridge. Retrieved on 27th January, 2024 from <https://EconPapers.repec.org/RePEc:cup:cbooks:9780521736602>.
- Udoh, U.S. and Udobia, U.J. (2023). Power Outage and Its Implications on Value Chain Along Aba and Itu National Grid, Comprising Uyo and Eket Metropolitan Cities in Akwa Ibom State. *Global Journal of Communication and Humanities (GJCH)*, Vol.2, Issue 2, (pp.101-127).
- V., (1996). *The Mafia Manager: A Guide to the Corporate Machiavelli*. St. Martin's Griffin, New York.